

Effect of Denaturants on the Speciation of Amino Acid Complexes—Computer-augmented Modelling Studies. Part-V. Cobalt-, Copper- and Zinc(II) Complexes of L-Ornithine in Water-Urea Mixtures[#]

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The speciation of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of L-ornithine has been studied in varying concentrations (0–36.83%, w/w) of urea solutions maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ at 303 K. Titrations have been performed with a wide range of metal-to-ligand ratios (1 : 1.6 – 1 : 5.3). The primary alkalimetric data are pruned with a computer program SCPHD. The approximate formation constants thus obtained are refined with the computer program MINQUAD 75. The selection of best fit chemical models is based on statistical parameters and residual analysis. The active form of the ligand is LH₃⁺, and the metal-ligand species detected are ML⁺, ML₂, MLH²⁺, ML₂H⁺, ML₂H₂⁺ and ML₂H₄⁴⁺. Global stability constants are evaluated using ANOVA. The trend in β values of the proton-ligand and the metal-ligand complexes with the change in the dielectric constant of the medium is attributed to the changes in the electrostatic and nonelectrostatic forces.

In healthy human adult, about 400 g of amino acids are recycled daily through amino acid pools; only 75–80% are utilised for new protein synthesis. The remaining are used for energy production or eliminated. The primary step in these processes is transamination or oxidative deamination. The stripped off amino nitrogen is excreted as urea. The production of urea in liver (through urea cycle) is actively associated with a non-proteinaceous amino acid, L-ornithine.

Some of the transition metal ions like cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) are essential and any variation in their biological concentrations leads to metabolic disorders. Cobalt(III) is associated with cynocobalamin, a life-saving vitamin. But cobalt(II) is mildly toxic and it depresses the thyroid activity. A high cobalt diet may cause goitre and polycythemia and also impairs glycogen metabolism in liver which leads to cardiomyopathy. Liver plays the central role in copper metabolism. It sequesters and stores copper, converts it into a bile component and produces some of the copper proteins, including ceruloplasmin. Zinc is an essential constituent of alcohol dehydrogenase, an enzyme mainly associated with liver. From these facts it is obvious that the physiological activities of L-ornithine and these metal ions are associated with the metabolic processes in liver. Hence, the speciation studies on the interaction of L-ornithine with the Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in varying compositions of water-urea mixtures have been carried out.

Results and Discussion

Protonation equilibria : The protonation constants of L-ornithine in different water-urea mixture were calculated based on the alkalimetric titration data (Table 1). The protonation constant of urea¹ was reported as 0.1 at 25° and

0.1 M ionic strength and hence, it is less likely that it interferes with the present study.

Complex equilibria : The relation between the formation function \bar{n} (average number of moles of ligand bound per mole of metal ions) and pH gives some information regarding the existence of protonated species. If the formation curves overlap for different concentrations of the ligand for the same metal ion concentration, it can be in-

TABLE 1—BEST-FIT CHEMICAL MODELS OF ACIDO-BASIC EQUILIBRIA OF L-ORNITHINE IN WATER-UREA MIXTURES

$\mu = 0.16 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH readability = 0.01, temp. = 303 K

No. of titration curves in each percentage = 4

% (w/w)	pH range	$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2$ (SD)	$\log \beta_3$ (SD)	NP	U_{corr}
5.80	2.4–11.2	10.480 (0.003)	19.316 (0.005)	21.378 (0.013)	67	2.896
11.52	2.4–11.1	9.899 (0.005)	18.827 (0.006)	21.141 (0.017)	50	1.582
20.31	2.4–11.1	9.739 (0.007)	18.477 (0.007)	21.145 (0.021)	51	1.885
29.64	2.4–11.4	9.623 (0.004)	18.168 (0.004)	20.937 (0.011)	46	3.426
36.83	2.4–11.4	9.869 (0.003)	18.166 (0.007)	21.067 (0.009)	31	0.376

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP-m) * 10^8$; m = number of species.

ferred that there exist only unprotonated metal-ligand complexes. But the spread in formation curves suggests the possibility of coexistence of protonated and unprotonated species. The non-overlapping nature of formation curves in the pH range 6.0–10.0, indicates the existence of protonated species in that pH range. To validate this assumption exhaustive modelling was performed for some typical systems. Models containing different possible species were

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tried in exhaust modelling assuming the coexistence of the different equilibria. As the number of species increased, the model gave better statistics confirming the better fit. There was no further improvement in the fit on inclusion of some more species to the models that are reported in

ume, metal ion, ligand, alkali and mineral acid concentration in that increasing order affect the magnitude of stability constants.

Solute-solvent interactions : The plots of stepwise formation constants ($\log K^M$) versus solvent parameter (mole

TABLE 2—BEST-FIT CHEMICAL MODELS OF M(II)-ORNITHINE COMPLEXES IN WATER-UREA MIXTURES

$\mu = 0.16 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 303 K, pH readability = 0.01

No. of titrations in each percentage = 9

Urea %(w/w)	$\log \beta_{mlh} \text{ (SD)}$							
	110	120	111	121	122	124	NP	U_{corr}
Co ^{II} -ornithine (6.0 < pH < 10.0)								
0.0	5.89(7)	8.70(7)	14.07(9)	-	27.55(8)	-	202	2.93
5.80	5.95(3)	8.76(4)	13.98(4)	-	27.35(5)	-	188	4.48
11.52	6.35(3)	9.12(6)	13.57(6)	-	26.73(7)	-	170	6.84
20.31	6.39(4)	8.60(6)	13.40(6)	-	26.11(5)	-	163	1.92
29.64	6.71(4)	9.89(5)	13.87(6)	-	26.31(6)	-	160	2.07
36.83	5.67(5)	9.16(4)	13.47(4)	-	26.61(3)	-	153	2.43
Cu ^{II} -ornithine (2.0 < pH < 10.0)								
0.0	13.01(6)	15.42(7)	18.21(3)	-	34.49(7)	42.62(5)	346	1.33
5.80	12.51(7)	14.75(10)	18.08(2)	-	34.05(9)	42.37(6)	327	0.97
11.52	12.35(4)	14.33(7)	17.79(2)	-	32.76(8)	40.82(5)	302	1.42
20.31	12.58(5)	14.54(8)	17.66(7)	-	32.03(9)	40.10(8)	336	1.14
29.64	13.73(6)	15.67(9)	19.17(10)	-	33.88(11)	42.23(10)	292	0.56
36.83	12.05(8)	15.76(9)	18.48(10)	-	33.40(13)	41.65(11)	291	0.70
Zn ^{II} -ornithine (6.0 < pH < 10.0)								
0.0	6.90(6)	10.33(5)	14.43(9)	19.50(11)	-	-	215	1.03
5.80	6.91(4)	10.53(6)	14.41(7)	19.80(9)	-	-	207	4.29
11.52	6.87(3)	10.71(4)	14.18(5)	19.69(6)	-	-	199	2.78
20.31	6.59(5)	10.51(7)	13.85(7)	18.99(9)	-	-	197	7.40
29.67	6.71(4)	10.57(5)	14.25(6)	19.85(6)	-	-	150	2.93
36.83	6.85(4)	10.10(6)	13.87(7)	18.68(8)	-	-	165	1.91

110 = ML⁺; 120 = ML₂; 111 = MLH²⁺; 121 = ML₂H⁺; 122 = ML₂H₂²⁺; 124 = ML₂H₄⁴⁺.

Table 2. This indicates that the final model appropriately fits the experimental data. Such exhaustive modelling is performed for all the systems and the consolidated data of the finally refined best fit models are given in Table 2.

Effect of systematic errors : In order to have a cognizance of the effects of errors in concentrations of ingredients (mineral acid, ligand, metal and alkali) and initial total volume, on the stability constants of protonated and binary metal complexes, some representative systems were studied by introducing the errors in the concentrations of ingredients. The results of these emphasise that protonation constants of carboxyl group are more affected. This may probably be due to their lower magnitude than those for amino protons. Similarly, errors in concentration of alkali and acid, affect more than other factors. With the introduction of errors, the SD's are found to increase, inferring the appropriateness of experimental conditions and correctness of analytical concentrations. The data for metal-ligand equilibria (Table 3) show that the errors in total vol-

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ERRORS IN DANGEROUS PARAMETERS ON THE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Co^{II}-ORNITHINE IN 36.83% UREA

Ingred- ient	Error %	$\log \beta_{mlh} \text{ (SD)}$			
		110	120	111	122
Acid	0	5.67(5)	9.16(4)	13.47(4)	26.61(3)
	+1	5.44(5)	8.87(4)	13.37(3)	26.45(3)
	-1	5.94(6)	9.43(4)	13.58(5)	26.74(4)
Ligand	+1	5.71(6)	9.23(4)	13.49(4)	26.66(3)
	-1	5.62(5)	9.09(4)	13.44(4)	26.55(3)
Metal	+1	5.64(5)	9.13(4)	13.47(4)	26.59(3)
	-1	5.69(5)	9.19(4)	13.47(4)	26.62(3)
Alkali	+1	5.91(6)	9.38(4)	13.55(4)	26.68(4)
	-1	5.45(5)	8.93(4)	13.40(3)	26.50(3)
Total Volume	+1	5.67(5)	9.18(4)	13.47(4)	26.61(3)
	-1	5.66(5)	9.15(4)	13.47(4)	26.60(3)
All para- meters	+1	5.67(5)	9.16(4)	13.47(4)	26.61(3)
	-1	5.67(5)	9.16(4)	13.47(4)	26.61(3)

110 = ML⁺; 120 = ML₂; 111 = MLH²⁺; 122 = ML₂H₂²⁺

fraction, n_x or inverse of dielectric constant, $1/D$) for the protonation of L-ornithine in water-urea mixtures indicated a continuous decrease in the $\log K^M$ values with decreasing dielectric constant of the solvent mixture for carboxyl and α -amino groups. But it decreased up to a certain solvent parameter in case of γ -amino group, and further increase in co-solvent concentration resulted in the reversal

relationship between the stability constant and n_x (or $1/D$) (Fig. 1 is given for a typical system). Such linear segmented nature of the plot is a result of the dominance of different types of electrostatic forces operative in different ranges of the solvent parameter. In some cases, there is deviation from linearity even in the segments, which indicates the blend of both electrostatic and non-electrostatic interactions and the existence of different urea-water solvent species at different concentrations.

Distribution diagrams : Using the formation constants of the best fit model, distribution diagrams were obtained with DISPLO². This program can be used to output distribution contours in any required pH range and to study the effect of errors in stability constants or variation in the concentration of ingredients. This information is highly useful in choosing ingredient concentration to increase or decrease the concentration of selected species.

L-Ornithine has one dissociable carboxyl proton and its two amino groups can associate with two extra protons. Hence, the form of the ligand can be written as LH_3^{2+} in acid medium. The equilibria (Scheme 1) reveal that the

Fig 1 Variation of $\log K^M$ of Cu^{II} -ORN with (Δ) mole fraction and (o) reciprocal of dielectric constant in water-urea mixture

of this trend. This may probably be due to the domination of interaction between proton and nitrogen compared to that between proton and oxygen of water above a certain co-solvent parameter for many nitrogen bases.

The change in $\log K^M$ of complexes of L-ornithine with Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with variation of concentration parameters of urea (n_x and $1/D$) indicated a segmented linear

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Scheme 1. Protonation equilibria of L-ornithine

form of the ligand is LH_3^{2+} , LH_2^+ and LH in the pH ranges 2.0–4.0, 4.0–8.0 and 8.0–10.0 respectively. Therefore, the stoichiometric coefficients of metal-ligand complexes of L-ornithine will depend on the pH range of study. The present investigation was confined to the pH range 6.0–

10.0 for Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes, 2.0–10.0 for Cu^{II} complexes. Under the present experimental conditions, the predominant forms of the ligand are found to be LH_2^+ and LH , which limit the probable metal-ligand species to be ML^+ , ML_2 , MLH^{2+} , $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_2^{2+}$ and ML_2H^+ . The actual species that are found to exist are ML^+ , ML_2 , MLH^{2+} and $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_2^{2+}$ for Co^{II} -ORN and ML^+ , ML_2 , MLH^{2+} and ML_2H^+ for Zn^{II} -ORN systems (Fig. 2). In the case of Cu^{II} an additional $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_2^{2+}$ species along with ML^+ , ML_2 , MLH^{2+} and $\text{ML}_2\text{H}_2^{2+}$ was confirmed. This is quite reasonable, as, at pH as low as 2.0, Cu^{II} participates in complexation and at this pH the ligand is known to exist in the form LH_3^+ .

In general, the concentration of ML^+ species increased with increase in co-solvent content irrespective of metal ion, ligand and co-solvent, whereas the concentration of ML_2 species is almost unchanged. The concentrations of most of the protonated species have decreased as is given

Fig. 2 Species distribution diagrams of (A) Zn^{II} -ORN in 20.31% urea and (B) Zn^{II} -ORN in 36.83% urea for metal to ligand ratio 1 : 5.4.

in Fig. 2. These observations lead to the conclusion that, in general, the stability of protonated species decreases and that of unprotonated species increases with co-solvent.

As the ratio of analytical concentration of ligand to that of metal increases from 1.6 to 5.3, the concentration of ML^+ decreased and that of ML_2 and ML_2H^+ increased. But the concentration of MLH^{2+} remained unaffected. Further, it can be seen that with increase in co-solvent content, the pH range associated with the existence of these species shifted to lower values.

Experimental

Solutions of L-ornithine hydrogen chloride (E. Merck), cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) chlorides (E. Merck or Sarabhai) (all A.R. grade) were prepared in triple-distilled water. Urea (AnalaR) was recrystallised from triple-distilled water and dried at 60° for 2 h³ and its stock solution was prepared in water and stored frozen. The solution was never allowed to stand at room temperature continuously for more than 24 h⁴.

To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentration, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA) using the computer program COST⁵. The strength of alkali was determined using the Gran plot method⁶.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying amounts of urea maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm^{-3} with KCl at $303 \pm 0.05 \text{ K}$. An Elico LI-120 pH meter in conjunction with a glass and calomel electrode was used. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 1.5 – 1 : 5.3) of metal-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol dm^{-3} KOH. Other experimental details are given elsewhere⁷.

The approximate stability constants of protonation or complexation of L-ornithine were calculated with the computer program SCPHD⁵. The best-fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares analysis using MINQUAD 75⁸. The variation of stepwise protonation constant was analysed on electrostatic grounds using ESOCE⁵ and on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

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